

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Nature of the Decomposition Product of Ethereal Blue Chromium Peroxychromate

(SMT.) R. B. PILLAI*, T. P. SAHAI** & C. V. P. PILLAI***

Department of Chemistry, Government Engineering College, Jabalpur

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ALTHOUGH many attempts¹⁻⁵ have been made in the past to study the decomposition product of the ethereal blue chromium peroxychromate, no conclusive evidence for the nature of the actual product of decomposition in water has been forthcoming. An attempt has been made in the present communication to show from spectrophotometric studies that the said decomposition product in water is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

Experimental

The blue compound was prepared in the usual way³, the extraction being done in ether. Then, 50 ml of the blue compound was decomposed in 200 ml of distilled water free from reducing substances. The decomposition product (aqueous layer) was separated for the following spectrophotometric studies.

Estimation of Cr(VI) and Cr(III) in the Decomposition Product: The recommended procedure⁶ for the estimation of Cr(VI) spectrophotometrically is from the absorption studies of Cr(VI) complex with 1-5 diphenylcarbazide. Thus, by complexing the Cr(VI) of the decomposition product in water with diphenylcarbazide and noting its absorption, the concentration of Cr(VI) was ascertained from the calibration curve drawn for known concentrations of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions. Next, the Cr(III) of the decomposition product was oxidised as per the procedure recommended by Oelschlayer⁷ and the increased total concentration of Cr(VI) was similarly determined. Obviously the rise in concentration of Cr(VI) corresponded to the amount of Cr(III) originally present in the decomposition product. It was found that the amount of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) in the decomposition product was in 1 : 3 ratio. The Beer's law graph has been excluded for the sake of brevity.

From the knowledge of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ion concentration the absorption spectra of the decomposition product in water was compared with that of a solution of potassium dichromate of equal strength. There was great similarity between the two absorption curves, with maxima lying at 360 nm and 440 nm in the case of the water decomposition product.

Thus from the ratio between Cr(III) and Cr(VI) and the absorption spectra it can be concluded that the decomposition product in water of the blue chromium peroxychromate extracted with ether is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

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Polarographic Reduction of Indium (III) in 2,2' Dimercapto Diethyl Ether Media

R. S. SAXENA & S. S. SHEELWANT

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur

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THIS communication reports the polarographic reduction of In^{3+} in 2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether, determination, of its kinetic parameters at various concentrations of ligand and temperatures and the values of thermodynamic functions for the electrode reaction.

2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether (referred herein as $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$) was supplied by Evan's Chemicals, Inc., N.Y., and other chemicals were of Anal-R (BDH) grade. The entire study was carried out in 40% ethanolic media at pH = 4.0 and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M$. NaClO_4 and Triton X-100 were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. The capillary of the manual polarograph had the following characteristics, $m = 2.652$ mg/sec, $t = 2.65$ sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.253$ $\text{mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/2}$. The experimental procedure and the methods adopted have been described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

$\text{In}(\text{III})$ ions produced cathodic waves in presence of 2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether. The plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ vs. E_{de} for the waves were straight lines but their slopes were not in agreement to the theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the

* Lecturer, Government Polytechnic, Jabalpur.

** Lecturer, Government Multipurpose Model Higher Secondary School, Jabalpur.

*** Senior author.

electrode reaction. The effects of Hg-pressure and temperature revealed that i_d increased linearly with $effh^{1/2}$ and the temperature coefficient of i_d is 1.11% per degree. All these observations indicate the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves.

The values of transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) for the electrode reduction of In^{3+} in $R(SH)_2$ have been determined at various concentrations of ligand (0.02–0.10M) and temperatures (25°–45°) by Koutecky's² method as extended by Meites and Israel³. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential and decrease in i_d with increase in $[R(SH)_2]$ (Table 1) indicate the complex formation between metal ions and the ligand. It may also be observed (Table 1) that the rate of the electrode process increases with temperature and $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards less negative potential supporting the irreversible nature of the waves.

TABLE I

Values of i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn and $K_{f,h}^0$ at various $R(SH)_2$ concentrations and temperatures

$[R(SH)_2]$ (M)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)	αn	$K_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0.02	11.20	0.658	1.51	0.31×10^{-13}
0.04	11.15	0.665	1.39	1.38×10^{-13}
0.06	11.10	0.672	1.29	4.67×10^{-13}
0.08	11.00	0.678	1.23	9.81×10^{-13}
0.10	10.95	0.684	1.18	14.68×10^{-13}
Temp.(°C)				
25	11.25	0.652	1.548	2.22×10^{-14}
30	11.90	0.628	1.427	6.26×10^{-13}
35	12.60	0.606	1.290	1.53×10^{-11}
40	13.25	0.586	1.231	9.72×10^{-11}
45	14.00	0.566	1.204	3.79×10^{-10}

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the electrode reaction have been determined⁴ at 25° and found to be 25.48 Kcal/mole, 44.61 Kcal/mole and 64.19 Cal/mole/degree respectively.

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Brucine and *o*-Phenylenediamine Complexes of Blue Perchromate : A Physico-Chemical Study

O. P. KULSHRESTHA* & D. R. SINGH

Chemical Laboratories, R. B. S. College, Agra

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COMPLEXES of the blue perchromate with different nitrogenous bases have been studied earlier¹⁻³. Magnetic measurements of red and blue perchromates have been done by Tjabbes², Klemm and Werth¹⁰. Bhatnagar, Prakash and Hamid¹¹ and Tomar, Singh and Singh¹² have measured the magnetic moments of the complexes of the blue perchromate.

In the present communication some new complexes of the blue perchromate with brucine and *o*-phenylenediamine have been prepared and studied.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. Grade. Blue perchromate was prepared by Rai's⁵ method.

Brucine Complex: 50 ml of 1% cold ethereal solution of brucine was added dropwise to 50 ml cold ethereal blue perchromate. A dirty yellow ppt. was formed. After 2–3 hr it was filtered, washed with ether to make the complex free from the base and dried in a desiccator.

***O*-phenylenediamine Complex:** To 50 ml. cold ethereal blue perchromate, an excess of cold and saturated ethereal solution of *o*-phenylenediamine was added. A black ppt. was obtained on keeping the mixture overnight. The ppt. was filtered and washed with ether till the filtrate was colourless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

Determination of oxidising powers of the complexes: Definite weights of the complexes were dissolved separately in the minimum volume of 1N NaOH solution and the solution was made upto a definite volume with distilled water. Oxidising powers of the complexes were determined volumetrically as suggested by Tomar, Singh and Singh¹².

Estimation of Chromium in the basic part and determination of the oxidising powers of the filtrate: Chromium in the basic part of the complexes was estimated (i) volumetrically, and (ii) gravimetrically as described by Tomar, Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*). Oxidising power of the filtrate (obtained from the gravimetric method) was also determined by the method suggested by the above workers. The observations and the results have been given in Table I.

* To whom the enquiries should be addressed—Department of Chemistry, Dayanand College, Ajmer (Rajasthan).